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IDEAS AND TEACHINGS FOR THE CONCEPT OF SPIRITUAL AND MORAL EDUCATION OF THE YOUNGER GENERATION IN UZBEKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

The article discusses the idea of educating the younger generation, youth in the works of Eastern thinkers, educational scientists like Abdarauf Fitrat, Abdullah Avlani Jadid of Turkestan, including educational reform at the present stage of Uzbekistan. The author paid attention to the relevance of the study of political and legal doctrines, works of thinkers of the East, which has an important role in educating the younger generation in the spirit of patriotism and high legal culture. The study revealed that the family and the social environment of communication have a great influence on the formation of civil positions in young people. The role of mahallas, educational institutions, and the media is noted. The youth of Uzbekistan is characterized by a high degree of patriotism, which is expressed in love for the Motherland, selfless service and readiness to protect it.

The results of the study show that in the system of life values of young people today, one of the main priorities is education. This is expressed in the desire of young Uzbeks to constantly raise the level of education. This is indicated by the overwhelming majority of students in schools, colleges and lyceums, every second young man and girl with a higher education, with secondary and specialized secondary education, university students. In general, long-term studies of the dynamics of life values, morality and social attitudes of young people in Uzbekistan show that in the years of independence, young Uzbeks form new priorities in the system of values, interests and social norms. This is an active life position, autonomy, purposefulness, social mobility, which is reflected in their national self-awareness and sustainably positive social well-being.

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As we know, the change in the state-political and socio-economic system, not only in our country, but also in all countries of the world, has created a fundamentally new situation in the field of education. A new approach to the educational system and upbringing is being formed in society youth. The state of the current system of education can be assessed as extremely complex, which is associated with the collapse of the main elements of educational policy and values, the search for new guidelines in education and upbringing. Therefore, today one of the most acute and strategically important problems is the problem of education and upbringing of the younger generation in the context of globalization and a rapidly changing world.

The problem of education has come to the fore in recent years. Firstly - and this is the main thing, since the whole world is now going through a period of generational change, just as today Uzbekistan is a country of youth. Therefore, one of the most important issues today related to the formation of a new state and society, the implementation of youth policy, which has become an objective necessity - more than 60 percent of the population of Uzbekistan are young people.

Secondly, the problems of spiritual and moral education are connected with the fact that in the modern world a person lives and develops among many different sources of strong influence on him, both negative and positive (mass media, communications, extraordinary events in various parts of the world, natural disasters, etc.), which constantly fall on the immature intellect and feelings of a young individual, on his emerging sphere of morality. It is becoming increasingly difficult for the younger generation to figure out what is true for them and what is false. Spirituality and morality, as you know, is nothing more than the basis of a personality characteristic, which runs like a red thread through all his activities and behavior, legal relations, and it is not always easy to reveal such a fact. Thirdly, the next urgent task in the field of educational work with young people is the education of a behavioral culture, a culture of everyday life. A person, communicating with people around him, expresses his feelings, emotions, realizes himself in actions. Unfortunately, in modern conditions, the education of a culture of behavior, both at school and in other educational institutions, including universities, is clearly not in the place that is required. Often young people do not know how to control their emotions, do not think about how much their behavior causes discomfort to others, do not know the basic rules of communication. Work on the moral and legal culture of youth requires special attention.

First of all, it should be noted the need to form the spiritual and moral qualities of the personality of a child, teenager, young man, girl. The younger generation should grow up not on examples of violence, evil, cruelty, but on examples of kindness, respect for elders, parents, understanding the value of human life, responsibility for one's actions and deeds.

Particular attention should be paid to the work of instilling respect for people of other nationalities. Modern youth should form an understanding that the ethnic diversity of mankind is a wealth that needs to be protected, to preserve the diversity of cultures, customs, and traditions. A person from childhood should be brought up in a respectful attitude, both to his own nationality and to other nationalities. The culture of national communication is the most important direction of educational work in educational institutions, in higher education as well. The experience of working with young people shows that the problem of labor education is an actual problem in schools and universities. Unfortunately, in modern conditions, little attention is paid to the labor education of young people. The true meaning of labor in a person's life is not adequately explained to young people, and the young generation's attitude towards a decent attitude towards work, respect for a working

person, conscientious work, organization and self-discipline in labor activity are not being formed. Also, an urgent task in the field of educational work with young people is the education of behavioral and legal culture, the culture of everyday life. An important problem in educating young people is to introduce young people to a healthy lifestyle. Research materials, the practice of working with youth show that the younger generation today needs special attention at the state level, social, educational, educational and family relations. Since, the globalization of society shows that, with each passing day, the use of alcohol, smoking, drugs corrupting youth, destroying the health of the younger generation is increasing among young people.

The Renaissance in Central Asia resulted in the greatest achievements in the political, economic and spiritual life of society. During this period, political and legal sciences, new literature and art, medicine, philosophy, and a new aesthetic consciousness were created.¹

As of now, the state policy of women, including women, in Uzbekistan, to protect the legitimate and social interests of women, to ensure full participation of women in the political life of the country, to ensure gender equality and reproductive health, is highly appreciated by the world community, namely, the International Labour Organization, UNICEF, the World Health Organization.²

The article examines the most important issues of the formation of the rule of law and civil society in modern Uzbekistan. Uzbekistan has a rich experience of political life, features of political consciousness and develops in unique and difficult conditions. Thus, it turned out that it is wrong to copy a simple copy of the political experience of the Western world.³

The paper investigates the essence of spiritual potential as well as its role in modern society.⁴

In conclusion, I would like to note that this law is aimed at improving public administration in the field of youth policy, securing the powers of each entity participating in this process. At the same time, the adopted document expanded and established additional state guarantees that will stimulate the comprehensive development of young people in Uzbekistan, their involvement in private entrepreneurship, which has become the engine of the country's economic growth. An analysis of the study of the problems of the development of modern society shows that the problem of educating a new generation is among them one of the most important. Today, this is perhaps the most acute and critically significant problem, the solution of which determines the future of both our country and many other countries of the world. The relevance of the problem of spiritual and moral education is connected with the fact that in the modern world. Spirituality and morality, as you know, is nothing more than the basis of the characteristics of a person, which runs like a red thread through all his activities and behavior.

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